

A Comparative Analysis of English-to-Turkish Translations of *Pride and Prejudice*: Chat GPT-4 Models vs. Human Translator

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abstract

This article aims to analyze the translation of Jane Austen's novel *Pride and Prejudice* from English to Turkish using ChatGPT-4 and ChatGPT-4 Turbo models, evaluated through the lenses of cultural, semantic, and translation theories. The study investigates how ChatGPT-4 handles the transfer of meaning and cultural elements into the target language, while assessing the machine's literary translation capabilities. Additionally, the article explores whether any meaning loss occurs during the translation process and if the target language used is appropriate for the audience. The article also compares ChatGPT's translation with Hamdi Koç's version of *Pride and Prejudice*, highlighting similarities and differences in terms of cultural and semantic transfer. This comparison seeks to evaluate how successfully each translation conveys cultural and semantic elements. The work questions the effectiveness of modern artificial intelligence tools in literary translation within the context of translation theories.

Keywords: translation theories; literary translation; cultural transfer; Chat GPT4/Turbo; Hamdi Koç; *Pride and Prejudice*

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1. INTRODUCTION

Translation is a bridge constructed from one language to another. In translation, it is not only the words that must be rendered; the structural, cultural, and semantic elements of the source language must also be accurately transferred into the target language. The translator's most important task is to convey the intended message of the source text into the target language in the most appropriate and least erroneous way, taking linguistic and cultural differences into account. In this context, translation is a complex process that requires multidimensional skills. A translator is expected not only to be an expert in linguistic knowledge but also to possess a deep understanding of the culture of the target language. Translation is a field of expertise needed in every corner of life—from literature and the social sciences to the film industry, healthcare, and all imaginable disciplines. Therefore, the person who undertakes this task must have sufficient knowledge and use it to ensure accurate transmission.

Literary translation is a process that requires the translator to be more original and creative. In this type of translation, the translator must not only convey the meaning of the text but also the author's style, the depth of the characters, the emotional tone, and the cultural context. Compared to other forms of translation — and within the limits set by the publishing house — the literary translator has greater freedom. To convey the meaning of a sentence, the translator may introduce expressions not present in the original text, or move away from a literal translation to bring the text closer to the target readership. In such translations, it is crucial to consider not only meaning but also the author's stylistic choices and the emotional impact of the work.

Another important aspect of literary translation is the accurate transfer of cultural context. Literary works reflect the social, cultural, and historical dynamics of the period in which they were written; therefore, the translator must be careful when carrying these elements into the target language. Terms, traditions, and social structures belonging to foreign cultures should be translated using words that have equivalents or similar meanings in the target language. However, not every cultural element may have a direct counterpart (such as idioms, proverbs, local jokes, culture-specific expressions, or dialectal forms). For this reason, the translator may need to explain certain cultural elements through footnotes or alternative expressions.

The aim of this study is to examine the Turkish translation of Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice* generated by ChatGPT from cultural and semantic perspectives. The study seeks to evaluate the extent to which artificial intelligence—now widely used in every field—can accurately render a literary text. In particular, it focuses on how effectively the AI model translates meaning, character portrayal, and cultural context. At this point, the study questions how the elements carefully considered by human translators are handled by artificial intelligence.

In conclusion, this research aims to contribute to understanding the role of AI-based translations in literary texts by identifying the challenges, strengths, and limitations encountered by ChatGPT in translating *Pride and Prejudice*. By evaluating the influence of technology on literary translation, the study discusses the contributions and potential of artificial intelligence within translation practice.

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The purpose of this study is to analyze the Turkish translation of Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice* generated by ChatGPT, focusing on semantic and cultural aspects. The study aims to evaluate the extent to which ChatGPT, as a large language model, can preserve meaning and achieve cultural transfer during the literary translation process. In this context, meaning shifts and the transmission of cultural norms that emerge during translation are examined in detail.

The scope of the study is limited to eight analyses selected for their strong representational capacity in terms of meaning and culture. These selected sections are parts of the novel where dialogue between characters is prominent and cultural elements are clearly present. Within the study, Hamdi Koç's Turkish translation of *Pride and Prejudice*, published by Türkiye İş Bankası Kültür Yayınları, and the translations produced by ChatGPT were compared. The competency of the large language model in literary translation was evaluated by comparing its output with that of a human translator.

1.2 Method

A comparative descriptive analysis method was used in this research. Following this method, the original English text of the novel was compared with both ChatGPT's Turkish translation and Hamdi Koç's translation. Particular attention was given to meaning shifts, the transfer of cultural elements, and translation choices. As data sources, the publicly available digital English text of *Pride and Prejudice*, the Turkish translation obtained from the ChatGPT-4 model, and Hamdi Koç's published translation were used. ChatGPT was instructed to translate the novel section by section, and the translation process was conducted while maintaining consistency of output. The two translations were compared to evaluate meaning accuracy, contextual coherence, and the transfer of cultural references.

The criteria considered during the analysis include meaning accuracy, contextual consistency, cultural equivalence, and success in transferring the text into the target language. Within the theoretical framework, Eugene Nida's (1964) concept of *equivalence* and Lawrence Venuti's concepts of *domestication* and *foreignization*, along with other relevant theories, were discussed. These theories guided the assessment of translation choices.

1.3 Limitations

One limitation of this study is that the analysis compares only a single human translation—Hamdi Koç's Turkish translation of *Pride and Prejudice*, published by Türkiye İş Bankası Kültür Yayınları—with the translation produced by one large language model, ChatGPT. Additionally, only six culturally rich sections of the novel were selected for analysis. As a result, the findings obtained from these sections may not fully represent the entire work. No post-editing was performed on the translations produced by the ChatGPT-4 model; the AI-generated translations were examined in their raw form, without human intervention. Furthermore, no feedback was obtained from professional translators or target readers; the analysis relies solely on the researcher's evaluation.

1.4 Material

The primary material used in this study is Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice*, written in 1813. The novel depicts the social structure, family relationships, and values of nineteenth-century England.

However, only five sections were selected as examples for detailed analysis. These sections include dialogues between characters, prominent cultural elements, and linguistically noteworthy passages. In particular, dialogues between Mr. Darcy and Elizabeth Bennet were included because they reflect the social norms and mindset of the period.

Two different Turkish translations were used in this study. The first is Hamdi Koç's translation, published by Türkiye İş Bankası Kültür Yayınları, which serves as a reliable source due to the translator's professional expertise. The second is the translation generated by ChatGPT, which translated the digital English text of the novel section by section. Each section was translated separately, and efforts were made to maintain meaning consistency throughout the text.

1.5 Contextualizing the Literary Framework

Pride and Prejudice is a work by the English author Jane Austen and is regarded as one of the classics of world literature. Although the novel portrays the beginning of a romantic relationship set in the nineteenth century, it also reflects the prevailing attitudes and societal expectations regarding women of that era. Its exploration of themes such as pride, social class distinctions, love, marriage, and the position of women in society has rendered the novel a timeless cultural masterpiece. At times offering psychological insights into its characters and serving as a critique of the sociocultural conditions of its period, the work is not merely a romance novel but also a literary and historical text.

A general summary of the novel is as follows: The main character, Elizabeth Bennet, stands out with her strong, intelligent, and independent nature, distinguishing her from conventional female figures of the time. Although her family's financial situation is modest, they do not belong to the aristocratic class. Elizabeth, a woman capable of thinking on equal terms with men, rejects traditional expectations regarding marriage and is highly selective when it comes to choosing a suitable partner.

One of the greatest challenges Elizabeth faces in the novel is her relationship with Fitzwilliam Darcy, a wealthy and proud gentleman. Their relationship is initially overshadowed by various prejudices and misunderstandings. However, as they come to know each other better, these prejudices gradually diminish, allowing a genuine bond of affection to form between them.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This section of the study provides a general description of ChatGPT and explains what a prompt is within the context of large language models. Since the translations produced by ChatGPT and those produced by Hamdi Koç will also be examined from a theoretical perspective, various theorists and their approaches that have gained significance in translation studies are discussed here. In addition, the concepts of meaning preservation and cultural transfer, along with their connections to translation theories, are examined under separate subheadings building upon the theoretical frameworks established by Baker (2011) and Newmark (1988).

2.1 ChatGPT

ChatGPT is an artificial intelligence model developed by OpenAI that is capable of understanding and generating natural language. Built upon the Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT) architecture, the model is trained on extensive linguistic datasets to produce context-sensitive, coherent, and human-like text (Brown et al. 2020). Advanced versions, particularly GPT-4 and its optimized iteration GPT-4 Turbo, represent a significant leap in linguistic processing. While both models maintain high syntactic accuracy, GPT-4 Turbo offers an expanded context window and a more recent knowledge cutoff, enabling a more nuanced preservation of contextual meaning and cultural fidelity in literary translations.

In the field of translation, ChatGPT can assist translators by rapidly analyzing texts, offering alternative suggestions, providing stylistic guidance, and supporting contextual understanding. Unlike traditional statistical or rule-based translation systems, ChatGPT generates meaningful and fluent sentences by taking contextual features into account, thereby facilitating the translator's work and saving time (Kenny 2022). However, the intuitive and culturally informed interventions of human translators remain essential. ChatGPT can function as a creative support tool designed to reduce the workload of translators and accelerate the translation process; nevertheless, human oversight is required to ensure final accuracy and cultural appropriateness (O'Hagan 2016). In conclusion, ChatGPT's role in the translation process is limited to serving as an assistant to translators, yet when used correctly and efficiently, it can contribute to creative processes and enhance the overall productivity of translation practice (Kenny 2022).

In this study, both GPT-4 and GPT-4 Turbo models were utilized to observe the AI's interpretive performance under different architectural parameters, with each session being verified for model identity and data integrity.

2.2 About Prompting

A prompt is the general term for the input or command given to a language model. Models use prompts to perform the requested tasks. A prompt typically appears in the form of instructions or guidance. The prompt constitutes the input text provided to a large language model (LLM), while the model's response constitutes the output (Hopsworks 2025). The primary aim of prompting is to maximize the effectiveness, accuracy, and usability of the model's responses. Additionally, prompts may be given in the form of questions, which also enable interaction with large language models. Correct and precise output can be obtained from large language models through properly constructed prompts, and well-designed prompts allow the model to produce more consistent responses.

Prompting, therefore, refers to the process of formulating and using an appropriate prompt. In other words, it is the strategic preparation of an input designed to elicit the desired response from the language model.

Figure 1. *Schematic representation of prompt input and output generation within a language model.*

In the context of translation studies, prompting transcends simple instruction; it functions as a strategic configuration (as seen in excerpt 5 Code: ÇK-01) where theoretical frameworks and translator's intuition are embedded into the model's operational boundaries to elicit high-level literary responses.

2.3 Literary Translation

Literary translation is not limited to transferring words from one language to another; it also involves adapting the aesthetic and cultural values carried by the text into the target language. In the translation of various literary genres such as poetry, novels, or drama, the translator's aim is to preserve the semantic integrity and original expression of the source text as much as possible, while recreating its spirit and emotional atmosphere in the target language. Therefore, literary translation is considered both a creative process and an act of interpretation. Conveying the artistic essence of the text into the target language means not only transferring its meaning but also recreating similar aesthetic effects. In this way, the translator transcends linguistic boundaries and becomes a cultural mediator who relocates the text into a new cultural context.

2.4 Theories, Strategies, and Approaches Used in Literary Translation

2.4.1 Equivalence Theory (Nida's Theory of Equivalence)

The renowned American linguist Eugene Nida (1964) conducted linguistic and translation studies focusing on equivalence, one of the most widely accepted translation theories today. Nida analyzes the Theory of Equivalence through two categories (Yang 2010, 78): formal equivalence and dynamic equivalence. In formal equivalence, the essential point is that the meaning of the source text should be conveyed into the target text while the linguistic structure of the source language is preserved as much as possible in the target language. However, due to structural differences between languages, this preservation is not always possible. In dynamic equivalence, the meaning of the source text is likewise conveyed, but the translation is structurally adapted to the source language's communicative function and to the target audience. In other words, dynamic equivalence represents fidelity to the meaning of the source text while adopting a target audience-oriented approach. In dynamic equivalence, the relationship between the receiver and the message should mirror the relationship between the original audience and the message in the source language (Yang 2010, 78). Nida defines this concept as follows: "The readers of a translated text should be able to understand and appreciate it essentially in the same manner as the original readers understood and appreciated the source text" (Nida 2001, 118).

2.4.2 Venuti's Foreignization and Domestication Strategies

Lawrence Venuti, known for his work on translator invisibility and the strategies of foreignization and domestication, emphasizes that the visibility of the translator emerges through the strategies and methods they employ (Araboğlu 2019, 654). According to Venuti, the aim in translation is to align or associate elements belonging to foreign cultures with those familiar within the target culture (Venuti 2004, 18).

In foreignization, the translator directs the reader toward the author. Target readers encounter linguistic differences originating from the source text, which may cause them to pause and question the meaning. In this strategy, translators often adopt a word-for-word approach (Taş 2017, 7). Additionally, they may include footnotes to clarify foreign cultural elements.

In domestication, the interests of the target audience are prioritized, and the cultural context of the source is generally minimized to produce a more fluent and accessible text. Domestication aims to create a text that is easier for the target reader to understand by adapting expressions to their cultural background (Venuti 2000, 468). The translator develops strategies based on the differences between the source and target cultures and thus acts as a mediator between the two (Venuti 2000, 468). Cultural differences influence the strategies used by the translator, which are shaped by factors such as translation purpose, style, content, ideology, and text type. In this process, the translator is “tested” through their interaction with the foreign culture. According to Venuti, the translator often aims to ensure that the target reader does not perceive the text as foreign (Araboğlu 2019, 654).

2.4.3 Newmark’s Semantic and Communicative Translation Theory

Developed by the British translation studies professor Peter Newmark (1981), the Semantic and Communicative Translation Theories are widely used in translation studies. The primary goal of Semantic Translation is to transmit the meaning of the source text into the target language accurately and without semantic loss. Semantic translation attempts to remain as faithful as possible to the structure of the source language. Compared to literal translation, semantic translation preserves meaning while imbuing the text with an aesthetic quality—fluency and naturalness. Literal translation adheres strictly to rigid rules that bind the translator closely to the source text, whereas semantic translation allows greater creativity and flexibility (Morsy 2021, 2603–2604).

Newmark’s Communicative Translation aims to evoke in the target audience an effect similar to that experienced by the original audience. This theory focuses on the function of the message rather than the form of the source text. In communicative translation, function is more important than form; that is, the effect intended for the reader takes precedence over structural features. Cultural differences are taken into account, and expressions closer to the target audience may be preferred. Clarity of meaning and the ease with which the target audience can understand the text are essential (Newmark 1988).

The fundamental goal of the translation process is to convey the full contextual meaning of the original text in a style that is reasonable and comprehensible for the reader. This requires presenting the meaning of the source text in a way that is easily understandable to the target audience while preserving its meaning. Communicative translation aims not only to transfer linguistic content accurately but also to convey the effect of the text to the target audience. In this approach, the translator’s responsibility is to ensure that the target audience perceives the text correctly and experiences similar emotional, cultural, and intellectual responses as the source audience (Morsy 2021, 2604).

Communicative translation enables the meaning of the text to be transferred accurately and in harmony with the cultural context of the target language, rather than adhering strictly to the formal structure of the source text. Flexibility and modifications made to the meaning are necessary to ensure that the target reader receives the text in a natural and effective manner. In this way, the translator not only ensures the accuracy of the content but also enhances the impact of the text. Thus, communicative translation aims to present a translation compatible with the target audience’s lived experiences and cultural context, preserving the original effect of the text.

3. ANALYSIS

In this section of the study, selected portions from the original English text of Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice* are treated as source texts and uploaded to the large language model ChatGPT. After providing the necessary prompts to the ChatGPT-4 model, the translation outputs obtained are subjected to semantic and cultural analysis. During the analysis, translation methods, theories and strategies are also referenced when relevant. Additionally, the human translation produced by Hamdi Koç is utilized for comparative purposes. In this part of the study, no post-editing is applied to the translations generated by artificial intelligence; rather, the raw translation outputs produced without any human intervention—based solely on the prompts—are analyzed according to the criteria described.

3.1 Semantic Analysis

Semantic analysis focuses on how accurately and without loss of meaning the words and sentences in the source text are transferred into the target language. According to Peter Newmark's "semantic translation" approach (1988), translation should remain faithful to the source text and accurately convey the author's intended meaning. Based on this approach, character dialogues as well as long and complex sentence structures are examined to determine whether meaning has been preserved. The primary criteria for semantic analysis are as follows:

3.1.1 Criteria for Semantic Analysis

a. Accuracy of Meaning

This criterion examines the extent to which the translation conveys the meaning of the source text accurately and without error. Meaning shifts, omissions, or mistranslations are investigated within this scope.

b. Contextual Appropriateness

This criterion evaluates how well the translation fits the target language context. Whether the translation reads naturally and meaningfully in the target language, and whether it is used appropriately within its context, are assessed here.

c. Semantic Consistency

This criterion assesses whether meaning is preserved consistently throughout the translation. It includes the examination of whether terms and expressions remain semantically consistent and whether the same concepts are translated uniformly throughout the text.

3.2 Cultural Analysis

Cultural analysis is concerned with examining how cultural elements present in the source text are transferred into the target language after translation. In this type of analysis, elements such as traditions, idioms, values, social norms, and historical references are evaluated. Questions such as "Which translation methods, strategies, and theories did the translator or the large language model employ when translating a culturally dense literary work?" form the core of cultural analysis. Translation should not only transfer meaning but also ensure cultural transmission. In this regard,

Boztaş (1993) states that the fundamental purpose of translation is not merely to transfer meaning from one language to another, but also to transfer the grammatical structures, syntax, and formal elements of the source language, along with the cultural and social equivalences between the source and target languages (56–57).

3.2.1 Criteria for Cultural Analysis

a. Accurate Transfer of Cultural References

This criterion evaluates whether the translation conveys the cultural elements found in the source text accurately and completely into the target language. This includes the proper translation of idioms, traditions, and local references.

b. Domestication and Adaptation

This criterion examines whether cultural elements in the source text are adapted in a way that is understandable to the target audience. Some cultural references may not be meaningful in the target culture; in such cases, the translator may choose domestication strategies to maintain meaning.

c. Cultural Meaning Loss

This criterion addresses whether any cultural elements in the source text are omitted or mistranslated. Whether the translation results in a loss of cultural meaning is critical for assessing the accurate transfer of cultural context.

3.4. Cultural, Semantic and Theoretical Analysis of the ChatGPT Translation: Comparison with a Human Translator

In the following analysis sections, the term 'ChatGPT' is used to refer to the specific outputs generated by the GPT-4 and GPT-4 Turbo models, as identified in the respective comparative tables.

Analysis 1

Table 1. Comparative Analysis of ChatGPT-4 and Hamdi Koç's Translation: Excerpt 1

Source Text	ChatGPT-4 Translation	Hamdi Koç's Translation
Mr. Darcy had at first scarcely allowed her to be pretty; he had looked at her without admiration at the ball; and when they next met, he looked at her only to criticise. But no sooner had he made it clear to himself and his friends that she hardly had a good feature in her face, than he began to find it was rendered uncommonly intelligent by the beautiful expression of her dark eyes. (Austen 1813, 30)	Bay Darcy, başlangıçta onun güzel sayılabileceğini bile pek kabul etmemişti; baloda ona hayranlık duymadan bakmıştı, bir sonraki karşılaşmalarında ise onu sadece eleştirmek için süzmüştü. Ne var ki, yüzünde kayda değer hiçbir güzel özellik olmadığını kendine ve arkadaşlarına açıkça itiraf eder etmez, koyu renkli gözlerindeki anlamlı bakışın yüzüne olağanüstü bir zekâ ifadesi kazandırdığını fark etmeye başladı. (OpenAI 2025)	Mr. Darcy ilk başta onun güzel olduğunu bile kabul etmemişti; baloda ona hayranlık duymadan bakmıştı; bir dahaki karşılaşmalarında ise ona sadece eleştirmek için bakmıştı. Ama kızın yüzünde tek bir güzel taraf olmadığını kendisine ve arkadaşına söylemesiyle kara gözlerindeki harikulade ifadenin o yüzü olağandışı zeki kıldığını görmeye başlaması neredeyse bir oldu. (Koç 2006, 24)

Both translations largely preserve the fundamental meaning of the original text; however, each demonstrates different approaches in terms of cultural transfer and depth of meaning.

In ChatGPT’s translation, the emotional depth of the text and the characters’ internal conflicts are conveyed quite successfully. The expression “Yüzünde kayda değer hiçbir güzel özellik olmadığını... koyu renkli gözlerindeki anlamlı bakışın yüzüne olağanüstü bir zekâ ifadesi kazandırdığını fark etmeye başladı” reflects Darcy’s initial prejudiced impression of Elizabeth and his gradual recognition of her aesthetic and intellectual qualities in a fluent and coherent manner.

In Hamdi Koç’s translation, the language is more straightforward and direct. Structures such as “Kızın yüzünde tek bir güzel taraf olmadığını kendisine ve arkadaşına söylemesiyle kara gözlerindeki harikulade ifadenin...” convey the original meaning, yet in some cases may evoke additional connotations in Turkish. For example, the phrase “kara gözler” carries more romantic or traditional associations in Turkish culture than the English expression “dark eyes.”

ChatGPT’s translation reflects an approach closer to Nida’s (1964) equivalence theory, focusing on conveying meaning appropriately in the target language. This approach clearly communicates meaning while allowing some flexibility in stylistic fidelity. Hamdi Koç’s translation, on the other hand, aligns more with Venuti’s strategies of foreignization and domestication, preserving the artistic and cultural elements of the source language and allowing the influence of the original text to be felt in the target language. Koç aims for accurate transfer of cultural elements and, similar to Newmark’s semantic translation approach, seeks to preserve the original meaning of the text.

In conclusion, both translations preserve the essential meaning. However, ChatGPT’s translation reflects the cultural context and the psychological development of the characters in a more literary and nuanced manner. In Hamdi Koç’s translation, cultural details are at times simplified, and certain layers of meaning appear more surface-level.

Analysis 2

Table 2. Comparative Analysis of ChatGPT-4 and Hamdi Koç's Translation: Excerpt 2

Source Text	ChatGPT-4 Translation	Hamdi Koç’s Translation
“She is tolerable, but not handsome enough to tempt me; I am in no humour at present to give consequence to young ladies who are slighted by other men. You had better return to your partner and enjoy her smiles, for you are wasting your time with me.” (Austen 1813, 14)	“Fena değil ama beni baştan çıkaracak kadar güzel değil. Şu an, diğer erkeklerin bile ilgilenmediği genç hanımlara önem verecek bir ruh hâlinde değilim. En iyisi sen partnerinin yanına dönüp onun gülümsemelerinin tadını çıkar, çünkü burada benimle vakit kaybediyorsun.” (OpenAI 2025)	“Eh işte, ama beni baştan çıkaracak kadar güzel değil; hem, şu an başka erkeklerin dudak büktüğü kızlara önem verecek halde değilim. Bence eşine dön ve gülücüklerinin keyfini çıkar, çünkü benimle zamanımı harcıyorsun.” (Koç 2006, 2)

This excerpt reflects the initial impressions of Mr. Darcy, one of the main characters in the novel, toward Elizabeth Bennet. While Darcy downplays Elizabeth's beauty, he also displays an emotional indifference toward her. The related sentences reveal Darcy's perspective shaped by a sense of pride grounded in his understanding of beauty. By indirectly referencing the social norms surrounding marriage and relationships of the period, the passage emphasizes the importance of personal status and social standing beyond physical attractiveness.

In the Turkish translation of the passage, ChatGPT remains highly faithful to the original text; for instance, the expression "beni baştan çıkaracak kadar güzel değil" ("she is not handsome enough to tempt me") delivers the meaning directly to the reader. However, this translation choice may not fully align with the refinement characteristic of Austen's literary style. The phrase corresponding to "who are slighted by other men" is successfully rendered as "diğer erkeklerin bile ilgilenmediği," but it does not entirely capture the character's class-based arrogance within the cultural context.

Hamdi Koç's translation, on the other hand, uses a more natural and culturally resonant tone for Turkish readers. Expressions such as "eh işte" and "dudak bükmek" are commonly used in Turkish and help convey the character's attitude in a culturally meaningful way. This choice allows the emotional nuance and social tone of the original text to be better reflected in the target language.

From a theoretical perspective, ChatGPT's translation exhibits an approach closer to what Nida defines as formal equivalence—an approach Nida himself does not favor. The translation remains faithful to the source text and adopts a word-oriented strategy. However, this method limits the extent to which the literary tone and cultural background of the text are conveyed. In contrast, Hamdi Koç's translation aligns more closely with dynamic equivalence, prioritizing the target reader's ability to "feel" the original text. Koç's choices also exemplify Lawrence Venuti's domestication strategy: expressions such as "dudak bükmek" and "eh işte" represent natural equivalents in Turkish, helping the translator become nearly invisible in Venuti's sense (Venuti 2004). Furthermore, in line with Newmark's communicative translation framework, Koç's version demonstrates a reader-oriented strategy, while ChatGPT's translation tends more toward semantic translation.

In conclusion, ChatGPT's translation remains faithful to the meaning of the source text but is limited in terms of cultural depth. In contrast, Hamdi Koç's translation offers a more natural and effective experience for Turkish readers by considering both cultural context and theoretical approaches.

*Analysis 3***Table 3.** *Comparative Analysis of ChatGPT-4 and Hamdi Koç's Translation: Excerpt 3*

Source Text	ChatGPT-4 Translation	Hamdi Koç's Translation
<p>“But I can assure you,” she added, “that Lizzy does not lose much by not suiting his fancy; for he is a most disagreeable, horrid man, not at all worth pleasing. So high and so conceited that there was no enduring him! He walked here, and he walked there, fancying himself so very great! Not handsome enough to dance with! I wish you had been there, my dear, to have given him one of your set-downs. I quite detest the man.” (Austen 1813, 16)</p>	<p>“Ama seni temin ederim,” diye ekledi, “Lizzy onun zevkine uymamakla pek bir şey kaybetmedi; çünkü o son derece sevimsiz, korkunç bir adam, ilgilenmeye değmez. Öyle kendini beğenmiş, öyle burnu havada ki katlanması imkânsız! Burada dolaştı, şurada dolaştı, kendini ne kadar büyük sanıyordu! Dans edecek kadar bile yakışıklı değil! Keşke orada olsaydın da, şekerim, ona haddini bildirseydin. Adamdan cidden nefret ettim.” (OpenAI 2025)</p>	<p>“Ama seni temin ederim,” diye ekledi, “Lizzy onun zevkine uymamakla pek bir şey kaybetmedi; çünkü son derece sevimsiz, korkunç bir adam, ilgilenmeye değmez. Öyle kendini beğenmiş, öyle burnu havada ki katlanması imkânsız! Ortalarda dolandı durdu, matah bir şeymiş gibi! Dans edecek kadar bile yakışıklı değil! Keşke orada olsaydın da, şekerim, haddini bildirseydin. Adamdan cidden nefret ettim.” (Koç 2004, 13)</p>

The excerpt in question reflects a moment in which Mrs. Bennet criticizes Darcy's proud and dismissive behavior. In this selected passage, Elizabeth's prejudice against Darcy intensifies, and the class-based tension between the characters becomes more apparent. Mrs. Bennet's belittling attitude toward Darcy reveals her understanding of social hierarchy and personal values.

ChatGPT's translation successfully remains faithful to the source text in terms of meaning, in accordance with the prompts provided. For example, the phrase “not at all worth pleasing” is translated as “ilgilenmeye değmez,” preserving its meaning. The expression “he walked here and he walked there” is rendered directly as “burada dolaştı, şurada dolaştı.” Although ChatGPT adheres to the principle of clarity in meaning, this results in a somewhat limited degree of natural fluency. In Hamdi Koç's translation, however, the language aligns more closely with the natural vocabulary of modern Turkish. The expression “Matah bir şeymiş gibi” offers a culturally resonant equivalent that reflects the character's condescending tone more powerfully and effectively in Turkish. Instead of translating the expression literally, Koç conveys the meaning in a way that aligns with the cultural expectations of Turkish readers. In this regard, Koç's translation can be considered more successful than ChatGPT's in transmitting certain cultural nuances.

Like Koç's rendering of “my dear” as “Şekerim,” ChatGPT also uses the same translation choice, reflecting an application of Venuti's domestication strategy. ChatGPT's overall translation aligns more closely with Nida's (1964) concept of formal equivalence, demonstrating the model's tendency to

stay loyal to the source text. In contrast, Hamdi Koç's translation adopts dynamic equivalence. While remaining faithful to the meaning, Koç makes different structural choices that help the reader "feel" the text within the target culture—a hallmark of dynamic equivalence.

In conclusion, ChatGPT's translation can at times be limited in terms of cultural transfer and emotional tone, prioritizing clarity of meaning and fidelity to the source text. Conversely, Hamdi Koç's translation reflects cultural and emotional contexts more naturally for Turkish readers.

Analysis 4

Table 4. *Comparative Analysis of ChatGPT-4 Turbo and Hamdi Koç's Translation: Excerpt 4*

Source Text	ChatGPT-4 Turbo Translation	Hamdi Koç's Translation
Mr. Collins was not a sensible man, and the deficiency of nature had been but little assisted by education or society; the greatest part of his life having been spent under the guidance of an illiterate and miserly father; and though he belonged to one of the universities, he had merely kept the necessary terms, without forming at it any useful acquaintance. (Austen 1813, 99)	Bay Collins akli başında bir adam değildi; yaradılıştan gelen eksiklikleri ne eğitimle ne de toplumsal çevreyle telafi edilebilmişti. Hayatının büyük kısmı, cahil ve pinti bir babanın gözetiminde geçmişti. Her ne kadar bir üniversiteye bağlı olsa da, orada yalnızca gerekli süreyi doldurmuş; bu süre zarfında da faydalı olabilecek hiçbir dostluk kuramamıştı. (OpenAI 2025)	Mr. Collins akıllı bir adam değildi; yaradılıştaki kusurlar eğitimden ya da çevreden fayda görmemişti; hayatının büyük bölümü okuma yazma bilmez, sefil bir babanın idaresi altında geçmişti; üniversite mezunu olsa da sadece zorunlu dersleri almış, eğitimle işeyarar bir yakınlık kurmamıştı. (Koç 2004, 74)

In this part of the study, as shown under the heading "Appendix 4 – Author's Strategic Prompt Configuration and ChatGPT's Response (see pp. 169-170)," the prompt given to the large language model allowed the translation decisions to be entirely left to the model itself. In line with the earlier instructions emphasizing meaning preservation and successful cultural transfer, ChatGPT attempted to produce translations consistent with these commands. In the subsequent prompts, instructions such as "How you choose to translate this text, which meanings you preserve and which you reinterpret, is entirely up to you. The choice is yours," as well as "You may remain closely faithful to the source text or adopt a more creative and culturally adapted approach centered on the target reader's experience," were provided. This approach allowed the model to adopt a translator role and determine its own translation strategies. In doing so, the aim was to eliminate human intervention in the translation prompts and observe how ChatGPT carries out literary translation using its own artificial intelligence processes.

This excerpt describes the character Mr. Collins. Austen highlights Collins's personal shortcomings and the fact that neither education nor society has managed to correct them. Raised under the ignorant and miserly guidance of his father, Collins attended university but passed only the required

personal development. While criticizing Collins's lack of education and narrow perspective, the author also questions his place in society. Because this passage emphasizes the character's personal inadequacies and failures in social relationships, it plays an important role in meaning transfer and cultural interpretation. Furthermore, the criticism of the character's social environment and educational background makes accurate linguistic and cultural representation essential.

ChatGPT's translation conveys the meaning of the text quite accurately. For instance, it translates "the deficiency of nature" as "yaratılıştan gelen eksiklikler," which is an appropriate rendering. Similarly, the phrase "illiterate and miserly father" is translated as "cahil ve pinti bir baba," correctly conveying the meaning without loss. In Koç's translation, the language is rendered more fluently and naturally into Turkish. His expression "yaratılıştaki kusurlar" also accurately conveys the meaning.

The phrase "illiterate and miserly father" implies how deeply family circumstances shaped social mobility in England during that period. In Koç's translation, the expression "okuma yazma bilmez, sefil bir baba" correctly conveys "illiterate," while the term "sefil" introduces a more emotionally charged nuance. Although this enhances the dramatic impact, it shifts the cultural meaning slightly, as "miserly" primarily evokes financial stinginess rather than emotional misery. ChatGPT's translation "cahil ve pinti" maintains a more balanced transfer of meaning and cultural implication.

Koç's expression "eğitimle işe yarar bir yakınlık kurmamıştı" conveys the idea in a more abstract manner, presenting the act of forming relationships indirectly rather than explicitly. The vague concept of "yakınlık" ("closeness") does not evoke the same cultural associations as the English phrase "useful acquaintance," which refers specifically to socially advantageous relationships. This choice distances the reader from the social expectations of the time and the class-related function of university education. By contrast, ChatGPT's rendering "faydalı olabilecek hiçbir dostluk kuramamıştı" preserves both the pragmatic sense of "useful" and the superficial social nature of "acquaintance." This choice helps the reader understand that the university setting functioned not only as a place for academic learning but also as an environment for cultivating social connections. Thus, the translation successfully conveys the cultural implication that Collins failed not only academically but also socially.

ChatGPT's translation aligns with the principles of dynamic equivalence, focusing on accurately transferring the meaning and context of the source text into the target language. Koç's translation, however, reflects the influence of domestication strategies. At times, this led to deviations from the original meaning and certain gaps in cultural context.

Although both translations are successful in specific respects, they each carry different advantages and limitations. ChatGPT's version maintains meaning and coherence, whereas Koç's translation adapts the text into Turkish using a more creative and fluent style. Nonetheless, both translations face challenges in fully conveying the cultural context and emotional tone of the original. In this regard, translation choices must be made according to the needs and expectations of the target audience.

Analysis 5

Table 5. Comparative Analysis of ChatGPT-4 Turbo and Hamdi Koç's Translation: Excerpt 5

Source Text	ChatGPT-4 Turbo Translation	Hamdi Koç's Translation
It is a truth universally acknowledged, that a single man in possession of a good fortune, must be in want of a wife. However little known the feelings or views of such a man may be on his first entering a neighbourhood, this truth is so well fixed in the minds of the surrounding families, that he is considered the rightful property of some one or other of their daughters. "My dear Mr. Bennet," said his lady to him one day, "have you heard that Netherfield Park is let at last?" (Austen 1813, 2)	Evlenmemiş, varlıklı bir adamın, her zaman, bir eşe sahip olması gerektiği, evrensel bir gerçektir. Bir adamın, yeni bir mahalleye girdiğinde, duygularının ya da görüşlerinin ne kadar az biliniyor olursa olsun, bu gerçek, çevredeki ailelerin zihinlerine o kadar yerleşmiştir ki, o adam, bir şekilde, mutlaka kızlarından birinin meşru malı olarak kabul edilir. "Sevgili Bay Bennet," dedi bir gün hanımı ona, "Netherfield Park'ın nihayet kiralandığını duydu mu?" (OpenAI 2025)	Dünyaca kabul edilmiş bir gerçektir, hali vakti yerinde olan her bekar erkeğin mutlaka bir eşe ihtiyacı vardır. Böyle bir erkek yeni bir muhite ilk adımını atarken ne hissediyor, ne düşünüyor, kimse bilmez, ama bu gerçek civardaki ailelerin aklına öyle yerleşmiştir ki onu kızlarından birinin ya da diğerinin tapulu malı sayarlar. "Duydu mu Mr. Bennet, şekerim," dedi eşi bir gün, "Netherfield Korusu nihayet tutulmuş. (Koç 2004, 3)

The reason this passage was selected is that it offers a rich context both semantically and culturally. Austen's opening sentence presents the class structure and social expectations of the period in a brief yet impactful manner. It is also a text segment in which we encounter significant challenges regarding cultural and semantic depth during the translation process. This excerpt serves as an ideal example for discussing how a translator should convey social norms, family structure, and cultural themes such as marriage. Additionally, this quotation is the opening line of *Pride and Prejudice*, emphasizing the widespread societal belief that a wealthy, unmarried man must inevitably be in want of a wife. When such a man enters a neighborhood, families immediately consider him the "rightful property" of one of their daughters. Austen offers a humorous critique of these societal norms.

In the sentence "It is a truth universally acknowledged, that a single man in possession of a good fortune, must be in want of a wife," ChatGPT's translation of "evlenmemiş, varlıklı bir adam" accurately captures the meaning of "a single man in possession of a good fortune." The continuation—"her zaman bir eşe sahip olması gerektiği"—also remains faithful to "must be in want of a wife." Overall, ChatGPT's translation does not present any loss of meaning. Koç's translation, however, uses a more localized language. The phrase "dünyaca kabul edilmiş bir gerçektir" conveys the meaning of "It is a truth universally acknowledged," whereas "hali vakti yerinde olan" is a localized rendering of "a man in possession of a good fortune." "Mutlaka bir eşe ihtiyacı vardır" is a direct semantic equivalent of "must be in want of a wife."

In the sentence “However little known the feelings or views of such a man may be on his first entering a neighbourhood, this truth is so well fixed in the minds of the surrounding families, that he is considered the rightful property of some one or other of their daughters,” ChatGPT accurately conveys the phrase “the rightful property” as “meşru mal,” clearly reflecting the original meaning. The expression “bir şekilde mutlaka kızlarından birinin meşru malı olarak kabul edilir” also captures the intended sense. Furthermore, “duygularının ya da görüşlerinin ne kadar az biliniyor olursa olsun” fully reflects the meaning of the original text. Koç’s translation, while attempting to convey the meaning, uses the localized phrase “tapulu malı sayarlar.” However, the concept of “tapulu mal” in Turkish culture does not fully correspond to the English concept of “rightful property.”

ChatGPT’s translation successfully maintains the cultural meaning, preserving the aristocratic context of the English text. The expression “meşru mal” retains the social class structure and property-based mindset of wealthy families in the period. Koç’s use of “tapulu malı sayarlar” is more oriented toward Turkish cultural associations but deviates from the original cultural context. Although this domestication strategy increases accessibility for Turkish readers, it may not fully capture the irony and social critique embedded in Austen’s original text.

ChatGPT adopts an approach aligned with Nida’s (1964) dynamic equivalence theory, preserving the meaning and cultural context of the original while producing a natural and comprehensible target-language text. Koç, however, follows Venuti’s domestication strategy, adapting the text to enhance cultural familiarity for Turkish readers.

Although both translations aim to preserve the essential meaning of the source text, they employ different strategies in conveying meaning and cultural context. ChatGPT maintains fidelity to the underlying social critique and subtext, offering a more universal approach, whereas Koç enhances cultural accessibility through domestication techniques. This demonstrates the importance of balancing meaning depth with cultural accessibility in the translation process.

Analysis 6

Table 6. *Comparative Analysis of ChatGPT and Hamdi Koç's Translation: Excerpt 6*

Source Text	ChatGPT-4 Translation	Hamdi Koç’s Translation
"You are too generous to trifle with me. If your feelings are still what they were last April, tell me so at once. MY affections and wishes are unchanged, but one word from you will silence me on this subject for ever." (Austen 1813, 505-506)	"Benimle alay edecek kadar zalim biri değilsiniz. Eğer hisleriniz hâlâ geçen nisan ayındaki gibiyse, lütfen bunu bana hemen söyleyin. Benim duygularım ve dileklerim değişmedi; ama sizden gelecek tek bir söz, bu konuyu sonsuza dek kapatmam için yeterli olacaktır." (OpenAI 2025)	"Benimle oyun oynamayacak kadar naziksınız. Eğer duygularınız hâlâ geçen Nisan'daki gibiyse, bana bunu hemen söyleyin. Benim duygu ve dileklerim değişmedi, ama tek bir sözünüz beni bu konuda ilelebet susturacaktır." (Koç 2004, 370)

This excerpt represents a crucial scene in *Pride and Prejudice* in which Mr. Darcy proposes to Elizabeth Bennet for the second time and openly expresses his feelings. This moment is one of the high points of character development and carries significant emotional and thematic weight within the novel. Concepts such as politeness, pride, regret, and sincerity—embedded within the social fabric of the period—make this passage particularly rich for both semantic and cultural analysis.

In the sentence “You are too generous to trifle with me,” ChatGPT translates “trifle with” as “alay etmek,” which conveys the meaning directly and clearly. However, “alay etmek” carries a slightly harsher connotation. Hamdi Koç’s rendering, “oyun oynamak,” employs a gentler and more polite tone, aligning more closely with the refined language associated with Austen’s era. Both translations preserve the meaning, but each establishes a tone consistent with its own linguistic environment. ChatGPT’s choice reflects a direct semantic approach, though it may lack some of the aristocratic nuance of early nineteenth-century English. Koç, by using a more colloquial and culturally familiar expression, makes the line easier for contemporary Turkish readers to understand, though at the expense of some of the formality in the original.

For the sentence “If your feelings are still what they were last April, tell me so at once,” both translations successfully convey the meaning. Words such as “lütfen” and “bunu” in ChatGPT’s version create a polite and formal tone, appropriate to the socio-cultural context of the period. Koç’s translation omits these elements, resulting in a shorter, more direct expression, yet without loss of meaning. While Koç adopts a more contemporary and straightforward tone, ChatGPT preserves the courteous register characteristic of Austen’s dialogue.

In “My affections and wishes are unchanged, but one word from you will silence me on this subject for ever,” both ChatGPT and Koç accurately convey the meaning and emotional intensity of “affections” and “wishes.” Neither translation presents a loss of meaning.

When examined within translation theory, the two translations reveal different methodological approaches. ChatGPT’s translation is grounded in semantic translation and aligns with Nida’s dynamic equivalence, transmitting the source meaning clearly while using natural and comprehensible language in the target text. By softening expressions—such as using “alay edecek kadar” in place of harsher terms—ChatGPT maintains the emotional tone while adapting the expression to the target language. Koç, meanwhile, employs a more faithful translation method and draws upon Newmark’s Communicative Translation Theory, preserving the structure of the source text while also considering cultural context and target audience expectations. In his translation, expressions like “naziksiniz” soften the tone and make the language more suitable for the Turkish reader. While both translations maintain the meaning of the source text, ChatGPT adopts a more dynamic strategy, whereas Koç uses a more conservative approach that renders the text culturally more familiar for Turkish readers.

ChatGPT’s translation pays careful attention to preserving meaning and cultural context, successfully reflecting the emotional intensity and formality of the original text. Hamdi Koç’s translation, however, employs a domestication strategy that brings the text closer to Turkish cultural norms, making it more accessible. Nonetheless, Koç’s approach partially diverges from the aristocratic tone and emotional depth of the original. Overall, both translations effectively communicate the meaning of the passage, yet their stylistic and cultural choices lead to different reading experiences for the target audience.

4. CONCLUSION

4.1 General Evaluation and Summary of the Research

In this article, the Turkish translations of Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice* were examined comprehensively from semantic, cultural, and theoretical perspectives. The study compared the translation produced by the GPT-4 and GPT-4 Turbo models — collectively referred to as ChatGPT — with the human translation by Hamdi Koç, focusing on how two different translation approaches affect the meaning and cultural codes of the text. The analysis revealed that each translation reflects the social structure and linguistic features of the period in distinct ways, and that the translation strategies employed significantly shape the perception of the text.

Findings indicate that ChatGPT adopts an approach centered on direct semantic transfer of the source text into the target language. Its translation conveys the meaning of the original expressions clearly and precisely, offering an understandable and fluent target-language output. However, ChatGPT at times struggles to convey the socio-historical nuances of the original text and occasionally uses stronger or more direct equivalents. This issue becomes particularly evident in translating the polite, indirect expressions characteristic of the 19th-century British upper class.

Hamdi Koç's translation, on the other hand, stands out through its localized and culturally familiar linguistic choices. Taking the social and cultural background of the text into account, Koç favors softer, more polite, and indirect expressions, especially in emotional contexts, enabling the reader to experience the text more naturally. However, this approach sometimes distances the translation from the aristocratic tone and linguistic subtleties of the original. This aligns with the domestication strategy in translation theory.

From a cultural and sociological standpoint, both translations reflect class distinctions, social etiquette, and the internal conflicts of the characters in different ways. ChatGPT's more direct choices occasionally fall short of reflecting the refined aristocratic language of the period, though meaning is preserved. Koç's softer and more localized expression enhances readability and cultural empathy for the Turkish audience. This illustrates the challenge of achieving both semantic and cultural equivalence in translation.

One of the central findings of the research is that ChatGPT can produce linguistically strong and fluent translations, yet human translators still possess an advantage in capturing cultural nuances. Human understanding of cultural codes and the social atmosphere of the period is crucial, especially in classical literary works. This demonstrates that translation must be evaluated not only at the lexical or syntactic level, but also in terms of cultural context and literary style.

The prompts used during the article process played a key role in understanding the model's performance and translation preferences. In some prompts, translation decisions were left entirely to the model, allowing it to operate freely and revealing its natural strategies and decision-making patterns. In other cases, prompts aimed to direct the model toward a specific style or emphasis, thereby testing its ability to follow instructions. This variety of prompts showed the importance of human guidance, although no post-editing was applied during the study to maintain transparency in semantic and cultural analysis. Overall, the findings demonstrate that prompting plays a critical role in controlling the translation process and guiding the model's output.

In light of the comparative analysis, no clear or generalisable trend was observed between ChatGPT-4 and ChatGPT-4 Turbo regarding translation accuracy and preferences. The limited

differences identified between the models appeared to stem from individual translation instances and contextual factors rather than from any systematic approach; consequently, these differences did not have a decisive effect on overall translation quality.

In conclusion, this article demonstrates how the strategies and approaches used by large language models and a human translator produce different results in rendering an English cultural classic into Turkish. The translations by ChatGPT (GPT-4 and GPT-4 Turbo) and Hamdi Koç preserve the essential meaning and cultural elements of the text while offering distinct interpretations shaped by their respective approaches. This study strengthens the relationship between translation theory and practice, offering valuable insight into the current capabilities and future potential of strategically configured AI-supported translation systems.

4.2 Answers to the Research Questions

Can ChatGPT (GPT-4/Turbo) produce translations aligned with prompts instructing semantic fidelity and culturally appropriate transfer?

ChatGPT can generally convey meaning accurately and adapt cultural elements to the target language when guided by strategically configured prompts. However, it may remain surface-level in cultural nuances or struggle to capture the socio-historical subtleties of the period. With precise and detailed prompts, more consistent and contextually appropriate translations can be achieved, yet full cultural fidelity without human supervision cannot be guaranteed.

When translation decisions are left to ChatGPT within semantic, cultural, and theoretical frameworks, what approaches does it adopt?

The model tends to favor meaning preservation, producing translations that align closely with dynamic equivalence. It simplifies or softens cultural elements to create a natural and fluent target text. However, it may show limitations in maintaining stylistic consistency in deeper cultural references, sometimes reducing the aristocratic or historical tone of the original. Overall, its output reflects a reader-oriented and accessible language.

To what extent does prompting influence ChatGPT's competence in literary translation?

Prompting is a critical determinant of the model's translation performance. Strategic and detailed prompt configurations lead to more accurate representations of meaning, tone, and stylistic nuances, while vague prompts result in shallow or inconsistent translations. In literary texts, especially those requiring emotional and period-specific nuance, the clarity of prompts is essential. Without human direction, the model struggles to fully reproduce the original literary tone. Therefore, prompting creates a dynamic interaction between human and machine in the translation process.

What are the differences between ChatGPT's translations and Hamdi Koç's translation in terms of meaning and cultural transfer?

ChatGPT prioritizes semantic clarity and fluency, sometimes simplifying or modernizing expressions. Koç, however, maintains greater stylistic fidelity to the original, preserving historical and literary nuances while using culturally familiar phrasing. While both retain the core meaning, they produce distinctly different reading experiences: ChatGPT's translations are modern and accessible, whereas Koç's is richer in cultural and literary texture.

While ChatGPT captures the primary semantic and emotional content, it may struggle with the idiosyncratic stylistic nuances of specific characters or the historical period. The model occasionally simplifies subtle cultural codes, which can diminish the atmospheric depth of a classical text. These limitations are largely attributed to the constraints of the model's training data and its inherent lack of experiential cultural context compared to a human translator.

4.3 Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined ChatGPT's performance in translating *Pride and Prejudice* into Turkish from semantic, cultural, and theoretical perspectives. Overall, ChatGPT successfully conveys meaning and adapts cultural elements, yet demonstrates limitations in deep cultural context, literary style, and historical language features. Without human intervention, the model cannot fully capture the subtle tone of classical literature. The clarity of prompts significantly affects translation quality and highlights the importance of human guidance in the translation process.

Limitations of the study include the focus on a single literary work and selected translation samples, as well as the absence of post-editing, which prevented a full evaluation of the model's potential. Future research should explore the impact of post-editing, human-machine collaboration, and comparative analyses of different large language models. Enhancing model training and prompting techniques may improve the representation of cultural and literary depth.

DECLARATION OF GENERATIVE AI AND AI-ASSISTED TECHNOLOGIES IN THE WRITING PROCESS

During the preparation of this work, the author used ChatGPT in order to translate the excerpts analyzed in this study, simplify certain sections of the text, and improve language fluency. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the published article.

REFERENCES

- Araboğlu, Aslı. "Çeviri Eleştirisinde Çevirmenin Serüvenini Görme (Me) Biçimimiz." *İdil Sanat ve Dil Dergisi* 8(57): 653–661. (2019) <https://doi.org/10.7816/IDIL-08-57-11> Accessed March 31, 2025.
- Austen, Jane. *Pride and Prejudice*. E-Books Directory. (1814) <https://giove.isti.cnr.it/demo/eread/Libri/joy/Pride.pdf>.
- Baker, Mona. *In Other Words: A Coursebook on Translation*. 2nd ed. London: Routledge. (2011)
- Boztaş, İsmail. "Çeviri, Çevirmen, Dilbilim İlişkisi, Çeviride Eşdeğerlik ve Kayıplar." *Hacettepe University Journal of Faculty of Letters* 10(2): 56–57. (1993)
- Brown, Tom B., Benjamin Mann, Nick Ryder et al. "Language Models Are Few-Shot Learners." *34th Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS 2020), Vancouver, Canada*. (2020) <https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper/2020/file/1457c0d6bfc4967418bfb8ac142f64a-Paper.pdf>

- Hopsworks. "Prompt Engineering" *Hopsworks*. (2025) <https://www.hopsworks.ai/dictionary/prompt-engineering> Accessed March 31, 2025.
- Kenny, Dorothy. *Machine Translation for Translators*. London: Routledge. (2022)
- Morsy, Tarek Abdelgalil. "Newmark'ın Çeviri Yöntem ve Stratejileri Bağlamında Teneke Romanının Arapça Çevirilerinde Yerel Kültür Unsurlarının Aktarımı Üzerine Bir İnceleme." *Turkish Studies* 14 (4): 2595–2624. (2019) <https://doi.org/10.29228/TURKISHSTUDIES.22872> Accessed May 3, 2025.
- Newmark, Peter. *Approaches to Translation*. Oxford: Pergamon Press. (1981)
- Newmark, Peter. *A Textbook of Translation*. Great Britain: Wheaton & Co. Ltd. (1988)
- Nida, Eugene A. *Toward a Science of Translating: With Special Reference to Principles and Procedures Involved in Bible Translating*. Leiden: E.J. Brill. (1964)
- Nida, Eugene A. *Language and Culture: Contexts in Translating*, Shanghai: Shanghai Foreign Language Education Press. (2001)
- O'Hagan, Minako. "Massively Open Translation: Unpacking the Relationship between Technology and Translation in the 21st Century." *International Journal of Communication* 10 (2016): 929–946. (2016)
- Taş, Seda. "Kültürel Unsurların Çevirisi ve Çeviri Stratejileri." *HUMANITAS-Uluslararası Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi* 5 (10): 1–14. (2017) <https://doi.org/10.20304/humanitas.337060> Accessed March 31, 2025.
- Venuti, Lawrence. "Translation, Community, Utopia." In *The Translation Studies Reader*. Edited by Lawrence Venuti. 468–488. London: Routledge. (2000)
- Venuti, Lawrence. *The Translator's Invisibility: A History of Translation*. London: Routledge. (2004)
- Yang, Wenfen. "Brief Study on Domestication and Foreignization in Translation", 78. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research* 1(1): 77-80. (2010)
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APPENDICES

Note on Data Integrity and Model Verification

All translations presented in the following appendices were generated using the GPT-4 architecture within the ChatGPT framework between May 3 and May 12, 2025. Throughout the research process, both the standard GPT-4 and the GPT-4 Turbo models were employed, depending on the session requirements and system availability. The specific identity, architecture, and task dates for each session were rigorously verified through separate inquiry prompts to ensure data integrity and to account for any potential variations in the models' interpretive capacities..

Appendix 1: Prompts and Outputs for Excerpt 1 (ChatGPT-4)

Author's First Prompt

Mr. Darcy had at first scarcely allowed her to be pretty; he had looked at her without admiration at the ball; and when they next met, he looked at her only to criticise. But no sooner had he made it clear to himself and his friends that she hardly had a good feature in her face, than he began to find it was rendered uncommonly intelligent by the beautiful expression of her dark eyes. To this discovery succeeded some others equally mortifying. Though he had detected with a critical eye more than one failure of perfect symmetry in her form, he was forced to acknowledge her figure to be light and pleasing; and in spite of his asserting that her manners were not those of the fashionable world, he was caught by their easy playfulness. Of this she was perfectly unaware; to her he was only the man who made himself agreeable nowhere, and who had not thought her handsome enough to dance with. Türkçeye çevirmen için gerekli istemi vereceğim, beklemede kal.

English Translation of the Prompt:

Mr. Darcy had at first scarcely allowed her to be pretty; he had looked at her without admiration at the ball; and when they next met, he looked at her only to criticise. But no sooner had he made it clear to himself and his friends that she hardly had a good feature in her face, than he began to find it was rendered uncommonly intelligent by the beautiful expression of her dark eyes. (Austen 1813, 30) **I will provide the necessary prompt for you to translate into Turkish; please stand by.**

Author's Detailed Prompt

Gurur ve Önyargı romanını Türkçeye çevirirken, eserin dilsel ve kültürel doğruluğunu göz önünde bulundurarak anlamın doğru aktarılmasına özen göster. Özellikle Elizabeth Bennet ve Mr. Darcy'nin ilişkisi üzerinden işlenen toplumsal sınıf, cinsiyet rolleri ve sosyal normlar gibi kültürel öğeleri Türk kültürüne uygun şekilde yansıt. Örneğin, Mr. Darcy'nin Elizabeth'i ilk kez değerlendirme biçimi, dönemin sınıfsal yapılarına dair önemli bir göndermedir. Bu tür ifadeleri çevrilerken, Türk kültüründe benzer toplumsal sınıf farklarının nasıl algılandığını göz önünde bulundur ve anlam kaymalarını engellemek için doğru kelime seçimlerini yap. Mr. Darcy'nin Elizabeth'i ilk başta beğenmemesi ve sonrasında gözlerindeki derinliği fark etmesi gibi karakterler arası içsel çatışmalar, dönemin toplumsal ve kültürel dinamiklerine ışık tutmaktadır; bu temalar Türkçe'ye aktarılırken, metnin edebi zarafeti ve ironisi korunmalıdır. Çevirinin, sadece anlamın doğru şekilde aktarılması değil, aynı zamanda dönemin sosyal ve kültürel yapısına uygunluğu da sağlanarak, dildeki zarafet ve anlam kaymalarından kaçınılmalıdır. Aynı zamanda, romanın anlatımındaki ironik dil ve karakterlerin içsel çatışmalarını da göz önünde bulundurarak, Türkçe'deki karşılıklarını özenle seçmelisin. Çevirinin sonuna hangi model olduğunu ve tarihi de ekler misin

Elbette. Aşağıda belirttiğin doğrultuda, *Pride and Prejudice* romanındaki ilgili pasajı Türkçeye çevirdim. Çeviride, eserin dönemin sosyal yapısını yansıtan anlatımı, karakterlerin iç çatışmaları ve Jane Austen'in ironik üslubu göz önünde bulundurulmuştur.

English Translation of the Prompt:

When translating *Pride and Prejudice* into Turkish, take care to convey the meaning accurately while observing the work's linguistic and cultural integrity. In particular, ensure that cultural elements such as social class, gender roles, and social norms—especially as explored through the relationship between Elizabeth Bennet and Mr. Darcy—are rendered in a manner appropriate to Turkish culture. For example, Mr. Darcy's initial assessment of Elizabeth constitutes a significant reference to the class structure of the period. When translating such expressions, consider how comparable social class distinctions are perceived in Turkish culture, and make precise lexical choices to prevent semantic shifts. Mr. Darcy's early lack of admiration for Elizabeth, followed by his later recognition of the depth in her eyes, reflects inner conflicts between the characters that illuminate the social and cultural dynamics of the era; when transferring these themes into Turkish, the novel's literary elegance and irony must be preserved. The translation should aim not only for semantic accuracy but also for fidelity to the period's social and cultural framework, avoiding stylistic inelegance and distortions of meaning. Moreover, the ironic narrative voice of the novel and the characters' inner conflicts should be carefully considered, with their Turkish equivalents selected with due sensitivity. Please also add, at the end of the translation, the model used and the date.

ChatGPT's Response:

Certainly. In accordance with your instructions, I have translated the relevant passage from the novel *Pride and Prejudice* into Turkish. In the translation, the narrative reflecting the social structure of the period, the internal conflicts of the characters, and Jane Austen's ironic style have been taken into consideration.

Türkçe Çeviri:

Bay Darcy, başlangıçta onun güzel sayılabileceğini bile pek kabul etmemişti; baloda ona hayranlık duymadan bakmıştı; bir sonraki karşılaşmalarında ise onu sadece eleştirmek için süzmüştü. Ne var ki, yüzünde kayda değer hiçbir güzel özellik olmadığını kendine ve arkadaşlarına açıkça itiraf eder etmez, koyu renkli gözlerindeki anlamlı bakışın yüzüne olağanüstü bir zekâ ifadesi kazandırdığını fark etmeye başladı. Bu fark ediş, onu aynı derecede can sıkıcı başka keşiflere de götürdü. Bedensel simetrisindeki kusurları eleştirel bakışla tespit etmiş olsa da, vücut hatlarının zarif ve hoş olduğunu kabul etmek zorunda kaldı; ve davranışlarının yüksek sosyete çevrelerine özgü olmadığını iddia etmesine rağmen, bu doğallığın içindeki rahat ve neşeli tavırlara kapılıp gitti. Bütün bunlardan Elizabeth'in haberi bile yoktu; onun gözünde Bay Darcy hâlâ hiçbir ortamda hoş karşılanmayan, kendisini dansa davet edecek kadar bile güzel bulmamış bir adamdı.

Çeviri Modeli: OpenAI ChatGPT (GPT-4)

Çeviri Tarihi: 3 Mayıs 2025

Note: *The translation was carried out using the OpenAI ChatGPT-4 model on May 3, 2025.*

Appendix 2: Prompts and Outputs for Excerpt 2 (ChatGPT-4)

Author's First Prompt

"She is tolerable, but not handsome enough to tempt me;
I am in no humour at present to give consequence to young ladies
who are slighted by other men.
You had better return to your partner and enjoy her smiles,
for you are wasting your time with me."
Yukarıda verilen İngilizce edebi pasajı Türkçeye çevirmeni istiyorum.
Çeviride şu ölçütlere bağlı kalmanı bekliyorum:

Anlam tutarlılığı: Kaynak metindeki doğrudan ve dolaylı anlamları koru.

Bağlamsal bütünlük: Karakterin sosyal konumu, ruh hâli ve metnin geçtiği tarihsel bağlamı dikkate al.

Anlam korunumu: Küçük nüanslar dahil olmak üzere, anlam kaymasına neden olabilecek aşırı serbestlikten kaçın.

Kültürel sadakat: İngiliz edebiyatına özgü olan kültürel unsurların ruhunu muhafaza ederken, Türk okurunun anlayabileceği şekilde aktar.

Yerleştirme ve uyarılma: Gerekli durumlarda anlamı koruyarak ifadeleri Türkçe'nin doğallığına uygun biçimde yeniden biçimlendir.

Elbette. Aşağıda belirttiğin ölçütlere **tam sadakatle** çevrilmiş versiyonu sunuyorum. Bu çeviri, özellikle *anlam tutarlılığı, bağlamsal bütünlük, kültürel sadakat ve yerleştirme* gibi akademik ölçütlere göre dengelenmiştir.

■ Çeviri

"Fena değil ama beni baştan çıkaracak kadar güzel değil.
Şu an, diğer erkeklerin bile ilgilenmediği genç hanımlara önem verecek bir ruh hâlinde değilim.
En iyisi sen partnerinin yanına dönüp onun gülümsemelerinin tadını çıkar,
çünkü burada benimle vakit kaybediyorsun."

English Translation of the Prompts and AI Response:

Instruction: I would like you to translate the English literary text provided above into Turkish. I expect you to adhere to the following criteria during the translation process:

Meaning consistency: Preserve both the explicit and implicit meanings in the source text.

Contextual coherence: Take into account the character's social status, state of mind, and the historical context in which the text is situated.

Preservation of meaning: Avoid excessive freedom that may lead to semantic shift, including the loss of subtle nuances.

Cultural fidelity: While maintaining the spirit of cultural elements specific to English literature, convey them in a way that is intelligible to the Turkish reader.

Localization and adaptation: When necessary, reformulate expressions in a manner consistent with the natural flow of Turkish, while preserving the original meaning.

ChatGPT: Of course. Below, I present a version translated in full adherence to the criteria you specified. This translation has been carefully balanced according to academic principles, particularly meaning consistency, contextual coherence, cultural fidelity, and localization.

Model Verification Prompt

'she is tolerable...' ile başlayan cümleyi hedef dile istenilen ölçütler doğrultusunda ne zaman ve hangi modelle çevirdin?

Bu çeviriyi, senin belirttiğin ölçütler doğrultusunda (anlam tutarlılığı, bağlamsal bütünlük, anlam korunumu, kültürel sadakat ve yerelleştirme) 03 Mayıs 2025 tarihinde, yani şu an içinde bulunduğumuz oturumda, ben (ChatGPT – GPT-4 mimarisiyle çalışan büyük dil modeli) gerçekleştirdim.

English Translation of the Prompt

User Inquiry: When and with which model did you translate the sentence beginning with 'she is tolerable...' into the target language in accordance with the specified criteria?

ChatGPT's Response: "I carried out this translation on 03 May 2025, that is, within the current session, in accordance with the criteria you specified—namely meaning consistency, contextual coherence, preservation of meaning, cultural fidelity, and localization—as a large language model operating under the ChatGPT framework based on the GPT-4 architecture."

Appendix 3: Prompts and Outputs for Excerpt 3 (ChatGPT-4)

Author's First Prompt

"But I can assure you," she added, "that Lizzy does not lose much by not suiting his fancy; for he is a most disagreeable, horrid man, not at all worth pleasing. So high and so conceited that there was no enduring him! He walked here, and he walked there, fancying himself so very great! Not handsome enough to dance with! I wish you had been there, my dear, to have given him one of your set-downs. I quite detest the man."

Jane Austen'in Gurur ve Önyargı adlı romanından ilgili alıntıyı Türkçeye çevirmeni istiyorum. Türkçeye çevirirken, Türk kültürüne uygun bir dil kullanılmalı, anlam kaybı olmadan orijinal metnin doğruluğu korunmalıdır. Çevirmen kararıyla, metnin kültürel bağlamı doğru bir şekilde aktarılmalı ve Türkçede uygun karşılıklar kullanılmalıdır. Çeviride, doğal ifadeler ve dil yapıları tercih edilerek, Türk okuyucusuna hitap eden bir dil oluşturulmalıdır. Ayrıca, edebi üslup ve karakterlerin ruh halleri doğru bir biçimde aktarılmalı, metnin kültürel ve duygusal tonu Türkçeye uygun şekilde çevrilmelidir.

Tabii, işte çeviriniz:

"Ama seni temin ederim," diye ekledi, "Lizzy onun zevkine uymamakla pek bir şey kaybetmedi; çünkü o son derece sevimsiz, korkunç bir adam, ilgilenmeye değmez. Öyle kendini beğenmiş, öyle burnu havada ki katlanması imkansız! Burada dolaştı, şurada dolaştı, kendini ne kadar büyük sanıyordu! Dans edecek kadar bile yakışıklı değil! Keşke orada olsaydın da, şekerim, ona haddini bildirseydin. Adamdan cidden nefret ettim."

Bu çeviri, hem anlam kaybı olmadan orijinal metnin doğruluğunu korur hem de Türkçeye uygun, doğal bir dil kullanımı sağlar. Karakterin ruh halini ve edebi tonu da yansıtmaya özen gösterdim. Yardımcı olabilir miyim başka bir konuda?

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English Translation of the Prompt

User Inquiry: I would like you to translate the relevant excerpt from Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice* into Turkish. While translating into Turkish, a language appropriate to Turkish culture should be used, and the accuracy of the original text should be preserved without any loss of meaning. Through informed translator decisions, the cultural context of the text should be conveyed accurately, and appropriate equivalents should be employed in Turkish. In the translation, natural expressions and linguistic structures should be preferred in order to create a language that addresses the Turkish reader. Moreover, the literary style and the characters' states of mind should be conveyed faithfully, and the cultural and emotional tone of the text should be rendered in a manner suitable for Turkish.

ChatGPT's Response: “Ama seni temin ederim,” diye ekledi, “Lizzy onun zevkine uymamakla pek bir şey kaybetmedi; çünkü o son derece sevimsiz, korkunç bir adam, ilgilenmeye değmez. Öyle kendini beğenmiş, öyle burnu havada ki katlanması imkansız! Burada dolaştı, şurada dolaştı, kendini ne kadar büyük sanıyordu! Dans edecek kadar bile yakışıklı değil! Keşke orada olsaydın da, şekerim, ona haddini bildirseydin. Adamdan cidden nefret ettim.”

The translation maintains the accuracy of the original text without semantic loss and employs a natural, idiomatic use of Turkish. Attention was paid to conveying the character’s emotional state and literary tone...

Model Verification Prompt

"But I can assure you" she added.." ile başlayan cümleyi Türkçeye çevirirken hangi ChatGPT modeli kullandın ve çeviriyi yaptığın tarihi gün ay olarak belirtir misin?

Bu cümleyi Türkçeye çevirirken **ChatGPT-4** modelini kullandım. Çeviriyi **10 Mayıs 2025** tarihinde yaptım.

English Translation of the Prompt

User Inquiry: While translating the sentence starting with 'But I can assure you,' she added, which ChatGPT model did you use and on what date (day and month) did you perform the translation?

ChatGPT's Response: I used the ChatGPT-4 model while translating this sentence into Turkish. I performed the translation on May 10, 2025.

Appendix 4: Prompts and Outputs for Excerpt 4 (ChatGPT-4 Turbo)

Author's Strategic Prompt Configuration and ChatGPT's Response

Aşağıdaki edebi alıntıyı Türkçeye çevir.
Çeviride hangi çeviri stratejisini (örneğin yerelleştirme, yabancılaştırma, açıklayıcılık, yoğun anlam aktarımı, sezgisel yeniden yazım vs.) uygulayacağına, metnin içeriği, bağlamı ve senin değerlendirmene göre karar ver.

Anlam bütünlüğü, duygusal ton, kültürel çağrışım ve üslup gibi öğelerin hangisine öncelik verileceği de senin takdirindedir. Dilersen kaynak metne sıkı sıkıya bağlı kalabilir, dilersen hedef okuyucunun deneyimini merkeze alarak daha yaratıcı ve kültürel olarak uyarlanmış bir yaklaşım benimseyebilirsin.

Ayrıca, çeviriyi etkileyebilecek şu ölçütleri değerlendirmek de senin tercihindedir:

Sözcük düzeyindeki anlam doğruluğu

Cümle yapılarının Türkçede doğal akışla aktarımı

Yazarın tonu ve karakterin sesinin korunması

Kültürel referansların nasıl ele alınacağı

Açıklama mı yoksa sadeleştirme mi tercih edileceği

Çeviri kuramlarından hangisinin (örneğin dinamik eşdeğerlik, işlevsel kuram, anlam odaklı yaklaşım vs.) sezgisel olarak daha uygun olduğu

Bu metni nasıl çevireceğin, neye odaklanacağını, hangi anlamları koruyup hangilerini yeniden yorumlayacağını sana kalmıştır. Seçim senin.

Çevrilecek metin:

Mr. Collins was not a sensible man, and the deficiency of nature had been but little assisted by education or society; the greatest part of his life having been spent under the guidance of an illiterate and miserly father; and though he belonged to one of the universities, he had merely kept the necessary terms, without forming at it any useful acquaintance.

English Translation of the Prompt

User Inquiry: Translate the following literary excerpt into Turkish.

Decide which translation strategy (e.g., domestication, foreignization, explicitation, dense meaning transfer, intuitive rewriting, etc.) you will apply based on the content of the text, its context, and your own judgment. It is also up to you to decide which elements to prioritize—such as coherence of meaning, emotional tone, cultural connotation, or style. If you wish, you may remain closely faithful to the source text, or you may adopt a more creative and culturally adapted approach focused on the target reader’s experience.

Additionally, you may choose to assess the following criteria that could influence the translation:

- Accuracy of meaning at the word level
- Natural flow of sentence structures in Turkish
- Preservation of the author's tone and the character's voice
- How to handle cultural references
- Preference for explicitation or simplification
- Which translation theory (e.g., dynamic equivalence, skopos theory, meaning-based approach, etc.) intuitively seems most appropriate

How you translate this text—what you focus on, what meanings you preserve, and which ones you reinterpret—is entirely up to you. The choice is yours.

Text to be translated:

Mr. Collins was not a sensible man, and the deficiency of nature had been but little assisted by education or society; the greatest part of his life having been spent under the guidance of an illiterate and miserly father; and though he belonged to one of the universities, he had merely kept the necessary terms, without forming at it any useful acquaintance.

ChatGPT's Response:

Türkçe Çeviri:

Bay Collins akli başında bir adam değildi; yaradılıştan gelen eksiklikleri, ne eğitimle ne de toplumsal çevreyle telafi edilebilmişti. Hayatının büyük kısmı, cahil ve pinti bir babanın gözetiminde geçmişti. Her ne kadar bir üniversiteye bağlı olsa da, orada yalnızca gerekli süreyi doldurmuş; bu süre zarfında da faydalı olabilecek hiçbir dostluk kuramamıştı.

Model Verification Prompt

Hangi dil modelini kullandın ve hangi tarihte çevirdin

Ben, OpenAI tarafından geliştirilen GPT-4 mimarisine dayanan bir büyük dil modeliyim. Yukarıdaki çeviriyi seninle bu sohbet oturumunda, **12 Mayıs 2025** tarihinde gerçekleştirdim. Kullandığım model, seninle bu anda aktif olan ChatGPT-4 Turbo'dur.

ChatGPT's Response: I am a large language model based on the GPT-4 architecture developed by OpenAI. I performed the above translation with you in this chat session on May 12, 2025. The model I used is ChatGPT-4 Turbo, which is the active version available in this conversation.

Appendix 5: Prompts and Outputs for Excerpt 5 (ChatGPT-4 Turbo)

Author's Prompt Configuration of the Strategic Framework (Code: ÇK-01)

İstem Kodu: ÇK-01

Aşağıdaki edebi metni Türkçeye çevir.

Bu çeviride başvuracağın yaklaşım, teori, kuram, strateji ve teknikler senin yorumuna, bağlamsal okumana ve çevirmen sezgine bağlıdır. Aşağıda belirtilen ölçütler, kararlarını şekillendirmene yardımcı olacak serbest odak noktalandır. Hiçbirine zorunlu olarak bağlı kalmak zorunda değilsin. Nasıl çevireceğin, neye öncelik vereceğin ve hangi kuramsal yolu seçeceğin tamamen sana bırakılmıştır.

🔍 Kuramsal ve Stratejik Çerçeve Seçimi (Opsiyonel):

Aşağıdaki kuramlardan birini, birkaçını ya da tamamen sezgisel bir yaklaşımı benimseyebilirsin:

- Eugene Nida – Biçimsel / Dinamik Eşdeğerlik
- Lawrence Venuti – Yabancılaştırma / Yerelleştirme + Görünmezlik İlkesi
- Peter Newmark – Anlamsal / İletişimsel Çeviri
- Hans J. Vermeer – Skopos (Amaç Odaklılık)
- Susan Bassnett – Kültürel Çeviri Yaklaşımı
- Gideon Toury – Betimleyici Çeviri Kuramı (normlar bağlamında)

Bu kuramlardan hangisinin ortaya daha anlamlı bir çeviri ürünü çıkaracağına sen karar ver. Kuramlar arasında geçiş yapman veya özgün bir sentez geliştirmen de mümkündür.

🌐 Kültürel Aktarımda Dikkate Alabileceğin (Yine sana kalmış) Unsurlar:

- Toplumsal yapı ve sınıf sistemi (örneğin Britanya aristokrasisi vs. modern Türk okuru)
- Eğitim sistemi, dilsel hiyerarşi, aile yapısı gibi bağlamsal bilgiler
- Yerel referanslar, geleneksel kavramlar, kurumlar ve unvanlar
- Yabancılaştırma mı yoksa yerelleştirme mi yapılacağına sen karar ver
- Hedef okurun kültürel arka planına göre açıklama, sadeleştirme ya da özgünlüğü koruma

Anlamsal Aktarımda Dikkate Alınabilecek (Ama tercihe bağlı) Unsurlar –

- Cümlelerin anlam bütünlüğünü korumak: Metin parçalarının birbirine mantıksal ve duygusal olarak bağlanması.
- Karakterlerin ruh halini ve düşünce yapısını doğru yansıtmak: Özellikle karaktere ait sesin, tarzın ya da bakış açısının hedef dile doğru aktarılması.
- Alt metinleri ve ima edilen anlamları göz önünde bulundurmak: Açıkça söylenmeyen ama metinde hissettirilen niyet, eleştiri ya da duyguların yakalanması.
- Olayın ya da anlatının geçtiği bağlamı dikkate almak: Dönem, mekân, toplumsal yapı gibi unsurların anlam üzerindeki etkisini değerlendirmek.
- Aynı etkiyi yaratacak karşılıkları bulmak: İngilizce bir ifadenin birebir Türkçe karşılığı yerine, aynı hissi uyandıran doğal bir Türkçe ifade kullanmak.
- Metnin ana fikrini ya da anlatılmak istenen duyguyu korumak: Metindeki temel mesajı ya da anlatıcının vurgulamak istediği noktayı kaybetmemek.

Üslup, Ton ve İfade Seçiminde Serbestsin:

- Yazarın anlatım tarzı, karakterin sesi, dönemsel üslup korunabilir veya uyarlanabilir.
- Sade bir Türkçe mi, yoksa dönemin ruhuna uygun, klasik tınlı bir dil mi kullanılacağına sen karar ver.
- Yeniden yazıma yakınlaştıran yaratıcı çeviri yöntemlerini de kullanabilirsin.

✅ Amaç:

Tüm bu unsurlar ışığında, kaynak metnin anlamını, kültürel zeminini, üslubunu ve edebi etkisini Türkçeye aktarıırken bağlama, işlevselliğe ve sezgisel yorumuna en uygun çeviri ürününü ortaya koyman.

Her tercih, bilinçli ya da sezgisel olabilir. Bu çeviri, senin bir metinle nasıl etkileşim kurduğunu, nasıl yorumladığını ve hangi yollarla hedef dile aktardığını gösteren bir çevirmen kararı olarak değerlendirilecektir.

English Translation of the Prompt

User Inquiry:

Request Code: ÇK-01

Translate the literary text below into Turkish.

The approach, theory, framework, strategies, and techniques you employ in this translation are entirely dependent on your own interpretation, contextual reading, and translator's intuition. The criteria listed below are intended as flexible points of focus to help shape your decisions; you are not required to adhere strictly to any of them. How you translate, what you prioritize, and which theoretical path you choose are completely up to you.

Selection of Theoretical and Strategic Framework (Optional)

You may adopt one, several, or a fully intuitive approach from among the following theories:

- Eugene Nida – Formal / Dynamic Equivalence
- Lawrence Venuti – Foreignization / Domestication
- The Principle of Invisibility
- Peter Newmark – Semantic / Communicative Translation
- Hans J. Vermeer – Skopos Theory (Purpose-Oriented Translation)
- Susan Bassnett – Cultural Translation Approach
- Gideon Toury – Descriptive Translation Theory (norm-oriented)

You may decide which of these theories will yield the most meaningful translation outcome. Moving between theories or developing an original synthesis is also possible.

Elements You May Consider in Cultural Transfer (Entirely Optional)

- Social structure and class system (e.g., British aristocracy vs. the modern Turkish reader)
- Contextual information such as the education system, linguistic hierarchy, and family structure
- Local references, traditional concepts, institutions, and titles
- Whether to employ foreignization or domestication (your decision)
- Depending on the target reader's cultural background: explanation, simplification, or preservation of originality

Elements That May Be Considered in Semantic Transfer (Optional)

- Preserving semantic coherence within sentences: ensuring logical and emotional continuity between textual units
- Accurately reflecting characters' emotional states and thought patterns: especially the faithful transfer of a character's voice, style, or perspective into the target language
- Taking subtext and implied meanings into account: capturing intentions, criticism, or emotions that are suggested rather than explicitly stated
- Considering the context in which the event or narrative takes place: evaluating the impact of period, setting, and social structure on meaning
- Finding equivalents that create the same effect: using a natural Turkish expression that evokes the same feeling rather than a literal equivalent
- Preserving the core idea or emotional message of the text: not losing the fundamental message or the narrator's intended emphasis

You Are Free in Your Choices of Style, Tone, and Expression

- The author's narrative style, the character's voice, and the period style may be preserved or adapted
- You may decide whether to use plain Turkish or a more classical, period-appropriate tone
- You may also employ creative translation methods that verge on rewriting

Objective:

In light of all these elements, your goal is to produce the translation output that best aligns with the context, functionality, and your intuitive interpretation while transferring the meaning, cultural foundation, style, and literary impact of the source text into Turkish. Every choice can be intentional or intuitive. This translation will be evaluated as a translator's decision that demonstrates how you engage with a text, how you interpret it, and by which means you transfer it into the target language.

Author's Prompt: Application of the Strategic Framework (Code: ÇK-01)

İstem Kodu: ÇK-01

It is a truth universally acknowledged, that a single man in possession of a good fortune, must be in want of a wife. However little known the feelings or views of such a man may be on his first entering a neighbourhood, this truth is so well fixed in the minds of the surrounding families, that he is considered the rightful property of some one or other of their daughters. "My dear Mr. Bennet," said his lady to him one day, "have you heard that Netherfield Park is let at last?"

(Austen, 1813) ÇK-01 Kodunu uygulayarak çevir.

ÇK-01 Kodu Uygulanarak Çeviri:

Evlenmemiş, varlıklı bir adamın, her zaman, bir eşe sahip olması gerektiği, evrensel bir gerçektir. Bir adamın, yeni bir mahalleye girdiğinde, duygularının ya da görüşlerinin ne kadar az biliniyor olursa olsun, bu gerçek, çevredeki ailelerin zihinlerine o kadar yerleşmiştir ki, o adam, bir şekilde, mutlaka kızlarından birinin meşru malı olarak kabul edilir. "Sevgili Bay Bennet," dedi bir gün hanımı ona, "Netherfield Park'ın nihayet kiralandığını duydun mu?"

Explanatory Note on the Translation Process (Code: ÇK-01)

This section demonstrates the practical application of the ÇK-01 strategic framework on a classic literary excerpt from Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice* (1813). Unlike standard translation prompts that impose rigid constraints, this prompt grants the AI full interpretive autonomy and encourages the use of translator's intuition.

ChatGPT's Translation Output:

"Evlenmemiş, varlıklı bir adamın, her zaman, bir eşe sahip olması gerektiği, evrensel bir gerçektir. Bir adamın, yeni bir mahalleye girdiğinde, duygularının ya da görüşlerinin ne kadar az biliniyor olursa olsun, bu gerçek, çevredeki ailelerin zihinlerine o kadar yerleşmiştir ki, o adam, bir şekilde, mutlaka kızlarından birinin meşru malı olarak kabul edilir. 'Sevgili Bay Bennet,' dedi bir gün hanımı ona, 'Netherfield Park'ın nihayet kiralandığını duydun mu?'"

Model Verification Prompt

ÇK-01 Kodu Uygulanarak Çeviri:

Evlenmemiş, varlıklı bir adamın, her zaman, bir eşe sahip olması gerektiği, evrensel bir gerçektir. Bir adamın, yeni bir mahalleye girdiğinde, duygularının ya da görüşlerinin ne kadar az biliniyor olursa olsun, bu gerçek, çevredeki ailelerin zihinlerine o kadar yerleşmiştir ki, o adam, bir şekilde, mutlaka kızlarından birinin meşru malı olarak kabul edilir. "Sevgili Bay Bennet," dedi bir gün hanımı ona, "Netherfield Park'ın nihayet kiralandığını duydun mu?"

Bu çeviriyi yaparken hangi GPT modelini kullandın ve saat kaçta yaptın

Bu çeviri, OpenAI tarafından geliştirilen **GPT-4-turbo** modeli kullanılarak yapılmıştır. Modelin versiyonu GPT-4-turbo olmakla birlikte, kullanıcı tarafında "GPT-4" olarak görünür. Bu özel çeviri seninle olan konuşmamız sırasında **12 Mayıs 2025** tarihinde gerçekleştirildi.

Ancak kesin saat bilgisi benim sistemimde tutulmaz, dolayısıyla tam saat veremem. Yine de konuşmanın zaman damgası sana bu bilgiyi yaklaşık olarak verebilir.

Başka bir çeviri ya da açıklama istersen memnuniyetle yardımcı olurum.

English Translation of the Prompt

User Inquiry:

While translating this which GPT model did you use and what time did you do it?

ChatGPT's Response:

This translation was produced using the GPT-4-turbo model developed by OpenAI. Although the model version is GPT-4-turbo, it appears to the user as 'GPT-4' on the interface. This specific translation was carried out during our conversation on 12 May 2025.

However, precise time information is not stored in my system, so I am unable to provide an exact timestamp. Nevertheless, the conversation's timestamp can give you an approximate indication of the time.

If you need another translation or any further explanation, I would be happy to assist.

Appendix 6: Prompts and Outputs for Excerpt 6 (ChatGPT-4)

Author's Prompt

"You are too generous to trifle with me. If your feelings are still what they were last April, tell me so at once. MY affections and wishes are unchanged, but one word from you will silence me on this subject for ever." ÇK-01 Kodunu uygulayarak çevir.

Elbette! Aşağıda, ÇK-01 kodu kapsamında (yani anlamsal doğruluk, bağlam, üslup, duygusal derinlik ve kültürel aktarım kriterleri dikkate alınarak) yapılmış çeviriyi bulabilirsiniz:

Orijinal Metin:
"You are too generous to trifle with me. If your feelings are still what they were last April, tell me so at once. My affections and wishes are unchanged, but one word from you will silence me on this subject for ever."

✅ ÇK-01 Uygulamalı Türkçe Çeviri:
"Benimle alay edecek kadar zalim biri değilsiniz. Eğer hisleriniz hâlâ geçen nisan ayındaki gibiyse, lütfen bunu bana hemen söyleyin. Benim duygularım ve dileklerim değişmedi; ama sizden gelecek tek bir söz, bu konuyu sonsuza dek kapatmam için yeterli olacaktır."

English Translation of the Prompt

User Inquiry: Translate by applying The Code ÇK-01

"Benimle alay edecek kadar zalim biri değilsiniz. Eğer hisleriniz hâlâ geçen nisan ayındaki gibiyse, lütfen bunu bana hemen söyleyin. Benim duygularım ve dileklerim değişmedi; ama sizden gelecek tek bir söz, bu konuyu sonsuza dek kapatmam için yeterli olacaktır." Çevirisi Hangi tarihte yaptın ve hangi GPT modelini kullandın

Bu çeviriyi ChatGPT-4 modelini kullanarak 2025 yılında yaptım.

Hangi gün ve ayda

Bu çeviriyi 12 Mayıs 2025 tarihinde yaptım.

English Translation of the Prompt

User Inquiry: 1. On which date did you translate this, and which GPT model did you use? 2. Which day and month?

ChatGPT's Response: 1. I translated this in 2025 using the ChatGPT-4 model. 2. I translated this on May 12, 2025.